

**A RESEARCH ON THE PROBLEM OF PUPIL TEACHER (B.Ed.) IN ACQUIRING
THE SKILL OF USING BLACK BOARD DURING MICRO TEACHING**

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Abstract:

The new innovation like team teaching, simulated teaching, program learning and interaction analysis, 'Micro Teaching' is a very important mean for (pupil teacher) pre-service as well as in-service teacher to develop and improve their pedagogical skills with a small group of pupil within a very short time with very short content material. So far as the core-teaching skill is concerned, the pupil teacher (B.Ed. students) faced so many problems during micro teaching while acquiring the each and every skill. Hence researchers did study such a research on this problem with special reference to the Skill of Using Black board to find out the problems so as to give the remedial measures with analysis and interpretation of collected data with Simple Percentage Method through Questionnaire from selected sample with Purposive Sampling procedure out of total population of all the B.Ed. colleges delaminating to Raipur district only of Chhattisgarh state to complete the research work smoothly, successfully and innovatively to achieve the stated objectives correlating the aspect hypothesis so far as the Normative Survey Method of methodology of educational research is concerned.

Keywords : *Core-teaching Skill, Micro Teaching, Pedagogical Skill, Pupil Teacher, Summary Meaning.*

Introduction

The new innovation like team teaching, simulated teaching, program learning and interaction analysis, "Micro Teaching" is a very important mean for pre-service as well as in-service teacher to develop and improve their pedagogical skills with a small group of pupil within a very short time with very short content material. So far as the core-teaching skill is concerned the Australian Advisory Committee on Research and Development in Education have analyzed 140 skills, Allen and Ryan(1969) of the Stanford University(USA) have suggested 14 skills where as Baroda General Teaching Competence scale was evolved with emphasis on 21 skills. But Dr. B.K. Passi has prescribed 13 skills which were developed on the bases of researches of Passi(1976) then E.C. Singh(1976-79), Janjira(1978) and Department of Teacher Education, the NCERT. The model was developed by Dr. Passi, Shah and Others at the center of Advance Study in Education Baroda. The pupil teachers (in-service and pre-service teachers) of B.Ed. class have been acquiring all these pedagogical skills in general and the 13 skills developed by Dr. Passi in particular and 7 skills as prescribed by B.Ed. syllabus in special in Micro Teaching.

In Micro teaching, first the pupil teacher receives a live or taped demonstration of teaching skill. Then he teaches a micro lesson for 5-10 (small group) pupils taking a single concept. This Micro lesson is videotaped. Soon after the lesson, the pupil teacher views the lesson on the video tape. He also receives feedback from his supervisor and peers. Then the pupil teacher re-plans the lessons on the basis of the feedback received from the supervisor and peers and re-teaches the same content to a different group of pupil. After teaching, this lesson is again reviewed and feedback is given to the pupil teacher by the supervisor and peers. The cycle of micro-teaching (teach, critique, re-teach, re-critique) continues till the pupil teacher attains mastery over the particular skill. During this process pupil teacher faced a lot of problems while conducting a micro lesson. Hence in this research study researchers conducted a research on a particular skill i.e. the Skill of Using black board to find out the problems and suggest the remedial measures.

Operational Term

2.1 Core Teaching Skills:

Observation of class room, various research studies and different theories of learning specify a group of teaching acts or behaviors intend to facilitate pupils learning directly or indirectly which are basic to teaching i.e. a group of teaching skill is termed as Core Teaching Skills.

2.2 Micro Teaching:

Micro Teaching is a scale down teaching encounter, scale down in term of class size (5-10 pupils), lesson length (5-10 minutes) and teaching complexity to provide pupil teachers for immediate diagnostic evaluation of teacher performance developing and acquiring pedagogical skill.

2.3 Pedagogical Skill:

Pedagogical skill means all those skill which are meant to be develop teaching performance of the pupil teacher, by the pupil teacher and for the pupil teacher within himself for his better performance those are identified as like Australian Advisory Committee On Research & Development in Education 140, Allen & Rayan (1969) of Stand Ford University (USA) 14, Baroda General Teaching Competancy Scale 21 and Dr. B.K. Passi(1976) and associate has prescribed 13skill. Those are:-

- 1) *Skill of writing instructional objectives*
- 2) *Skill of introducing a lesson*
- 3) *Skill of fluency in questioning*
- 4) *Skill of proving question*
- 5) *Skill of explaining*
- 6) *Skill of illustration with example*
- 7) *Skill of stimulus variation*

- 8) Skill of silence and non-verbal cues
- 9) Skill of using blackboard
- 10) Skill of achieving closer
- 11) Skill of recognizing attending behavior
- 12) Skill of increasing pupils participation
- 13) Skill of reinforcement

2.4 Pupil Teacher :

In this research study the researcher termed as pupil teacher to all the B.Ed. Students of teacher training institution selected as sample and constituted the population of the research work.

2.5 Summary Meaning:

Summary meaning refers to the operational term as use of color chalk on different colored chalkboard and summary of effective use of blackboard as following respectively.

2.5.1 Summary of Effective use of Color Chalks :

On different colored chalk board, specific color chalk should be used for maximum contrast in acquiring skill of using black board effectively:

<i>Green chalk-board</i>	-	<i>White or Yellow chalk</i>	<i>G</i>	-	<i>W</i>
<i>Grey chalk-board</i>	-	<i>Yellow chalk</i>	<i>G</i>	-	<i>Y</i>
<i>Red chalk-board</i>	-	<i>Green or Yellow chalk</i>	<i>R</i>	-	<i>G</i>
<i>Orange chalk-board</i>	-	<i>Blue/Light green chalk</i>	<i>O</i>	-	<i>B</i>
<i>Yellow chalk-board</i>	-	<i>Blue chalk</i>	<i>Y</i>	-	<i>B</i>
<i>Rose chalk-board</i>	-	<i>Purple/dark blue chalk</i>	<i>R</i>	-	<i>P</i>
<i>Black chalk-board</i>	-	<i>Any Color chalk</i>	<i>B</i>	-	<i>A</i>

2.5.2 Summary of Effective use of Black-Board:

- B** = Be kind and use me.
- L** = Layout the PLAN in advance.
- A** = Arrangement of black-board
 Check LAG : L = Light
 A = Angle
 G = Glare
- C** = Check CERCA: C = Chalk of all colors
 E = Eraser
 R = Ruler
 C = Cane
 A = Any other
- K** = Keep it clean
- B** = Be judicious
- O** = Order = SOS (Stand on side)
- A** = Attraction by CUP :
 C = Color, Capital letters
 U = Underline
 P = Pointer
- R** = Writing with a BRUSH : B = Bright
 R = Readable
 U = Uniform
 S = Straight
 H = Horizontal
- D** = Drawing with a PEN : P = Purposeful
 E = Easy
 N = Neat

Hence black board is the oldest and best friend of the teacher who has been devotedly devoted devotion divinely dedicated to towards the teaching profession as a mission for the betterment of not only teacher but also pupil teacher for its best friendship not for only day time

but for whole time even in the night within the class room accommodation what the teacher can never does for acquiring the skill of using black board to develop the effectiveness of the pupil teacher to be an effective teacher effectively where the black board request its friend with its first abbreviation 'B' saying – 'Please be kind and use me for the betterment of the pupils and skill development of the pupil teacher i.e. my best friend reflects the naturalistic, idealistic, socialistic, realistic, pragmatics, existentialistic nature of the black board what makes to it as a living being better then a teacher in the non-living era as like all its abbreviations always request to the teacher to use effectively to be an effective teacher.

Objectives & Hypotheses

3.1 Objectives

- To find out the problems in acquiring Skill of Using Black board during micro teaching.
- To find out the reasons behind this problem while acquiring Skill of Using Black board during micro teaching.
- To suggest remedial measures to reduce and remove all that problems to develop the pedagogical skill.

3.2 Assumptions

- Pupil teachers have the problems of using accurate techniques of using black board.
- Pupil teachers cannot use each and every techniques of using black board effectively.
- Pupil teachers do not have the knowledge on the logical use of color chalks & summary meaning of effective use of black board.

3.3 Hypotheses

- If the pupil teachers get sufficient content knowledge on the logics and techniques of using black board, then they can acquire the skill of using black board effectively.
- If the pupil teachers get sufficient content knowledge about different techniques of using black board then they can acquire the skill of using black board accurately.
- If the pupil teachers get sufficient knowledge on techniques of using color chalks as well as summary meaning of effective use of black board then they can acquire the skill of using black board successfully.

Methodology

4.1 Method:-

Researcher selected and used Normative Survey Research method for this study.

4.2 Population:-

Researcher has selected all the pupil teachers of all the B.Ed. colleges in Raipur District of Chhattisgarh state to constitute as the population of this research study.

4.3 Sample:-

Researcher has selected one college by Purposive Sampling Method out of total population.

4.4 Tool:-

Researcher has used Questionnaire to collect data from the sample as relevance tool in the study.

4.5 Statistical Technique:-

Researcher used the Simple Percentage method for analyze & interpretation of the collected data.

Findings & Suggestions

5.1 Findings :

- Most of the pupil teachers have the knowledge about general uses of black board and objectives of skill of using black board.
- Most of the pupil teachers faced problems due to lack of summary meaning of effective use of black board and use of color chalk.
- Most of the pupil teachers faced problems due to lack of sufficient content knowledge about logical & technical use of black board and different techniques of using black board perfectly.

5.2 Suggestions

- 5.2.1 Teacher educator should educate the pupil teacher with sufficient content knowledge about micro- teaching, pedagogical skill, skill of using black board and a list of different techniques of using black board clearly.
- 5.2.2 Teacher educator should educate the pupil teacher with deep knowledge of techniques of using different types of techniques of using black board with color chalks and general uses of black board perfectly and effectively.
- 5.2.3 Teacher educator should prepare ideal lesson with suitable example to educate and motivate the pupil teachers to develop the skill of using black board with using color chalks, each and every types of techniques based on summary meaning of effectiveness of skill of using black board.

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